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Digital Transformation and Supply Chain Agility in an Emerging Economy: Mediating Role of Dynamic Capabilities

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of digital transformation on supply chain agility, and the mediating role of dynamic capabilities in the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility. The study which anchors dynamic capabilities theory explains how firms build, integrate, and reconfigure competencies to address the dynamic business environments. A quantitative survey design was employed with 385 respondents from consumer goods firms in Southwest Nigeria. Hypotheses were tested with simple linear regression and PROCESS macro (Model 4) for mediation testing. The findings revealed that digital transformation significantly influenced supply chain agility ($\beta = 0.789, p < .001, R^2 = .465$). Also, dynamic capabilities significantly mediated the digital transformation-supply chain agility relationship (indirect effect = 0.455, 95% CI [0.414, 0.497]). The study found that digital transformation alone is insufficient for achieving supply chain agility; firms must cultivate dynamic capabilities to effectively leverage digital investments for enhanced supply chain responsiveness. The study contribution to the body of literature is to provide empirical evidence from the context of an emerging market and offers practical implications for managers seeking to leverage digital transformation for enhanced supply chain performance.

Keywords:- *Digital transformation, supply chain agility, dynamic capabilities, consumer goods, mediation analysis, Southwest, sensing, seizing, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

The global business environment is shaped by exceptional volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA), fueled by swift technological progress, evolving consumer preferences, and unexpected global occurrences (Westerman et al., 2014). In this environment, the ability of organisations to adapt swiftly and effectively has become a critical determinant of survival and competitive advantage. Within this context, digital transformation and supply chain agility have emerged as paramount strategic imperatives for firms seeking to thrive.

The rapid evolution of digital technologies has fundamentally transformed how organizations operate, particularly in their supply chain management practices. Digital transformation (DT) is the extensive incorporation of digital technologies across all areas of a business, bringing about fundamental changes in operations, customer engagement, and value creation (Vial, 2019). It goes beyond simply adopting new technologies, but involves a comprehensive organisational shift that utilises data, automation, and connectivity to develop innovative business models and improve efficiency (Kane et al., 2015). In the consumer goods sector, DT has the capacity to transform supply chain processes, ranging from demand forecasting and inventory control to logistics and last-mile delivery, thereby enhancing agility and resilience (Tabrizi et al., 2019).

Supply chain agility (SCA) has increasingly been recognised as an essential organisational capability, enabling firms to respond rapidly to market shifts, disruptions, and unforeseen events (Christopher, 2000). It is characterised by flexibility, adaptability, and the capacity to reconfigure resources in alignment with evolving customer demands and market conditions (Gligor et al., 2013). Within the competitive and

often unpredictable consumer goods sector, particularly in emerging economies, SCA is pivotal for risk mitigation, cost optimisation, and ensuring consistent product availability (Swafford et al., 2006).

As the largest economy, and most populous country in Africa, Nigeria boasts a vast and dynamic consumer market, diverse consumer demographics, and a rapidly advancing digital environment (Adebayo & Oladele, 2019). Thus, the Nigerian consumer goods industry faces immense pressure to respond to the technological dynamics of this decade, given its fast-paced nature, short product lifecycles, and direct exposure to evolving consumer preferences (Fitzgerald et al., 2014). Businesses within the sector must adopt digital technologies to address operational challenges, achieve supply chain agility and expand their customer reach.

Dynamic capabilities (DCs), is the ability of an organisation to build, integrate, and reconfigure competences (internal and external) to address rapidly changing environments (Teece, 2018). DCs are essential for sensing new opportunities presented by digital technologies, seizing them through strategic investments, and transforming existing processes to achieve greater agility (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). The significance of digital transformation and supply chain agility is widely acknowledged individually. However, the pathways through which DT enhances SCA remain intricate and multidimensional. This complexity is further amplified by the role of capabilities that enable firms to effectively leverage digital investments.

Though the direct correlation between digital transformation and supply chain performance has been extensively studied; For instance, Queiroz et al. (2020) concluded that blockchain technology significantly enhances supply chain transparency and trust, Bag et al. (2021)

demonstrated that artificial intelligence applications improve demand forecasting accuracy and inventory optimization. Also, Kumar et al. (2018) showed that IoT implementation enables real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, reducing operational disruptions and enhancing responsiveness etc. The degree to which these digital initiatives drive improvements in supply chain agility, and the mediating influence of dynamic capabilities in this relationship, remains insufficiently explored especially in Nigeria's consumer goods sector. By addressing this critical area, the research seeks to provide valuable theoretical contributions to the body of knowledge on supply chain management, digital transformation, and strategic management. As well as offer practical implications for managers and policymakers in the Nigerian consumer goods industry. The remaining sections of this paper will detail a comprehensive literature review, methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusion.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Digital Transformation and Supply Chain Management

Digital transformation (DT) involves embedding digital technologies like Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, blockchain, cloud computing, and advanced analytics across all facets of a business, leading to fundamental changes in its operations and the way it delivers value to customers (Fitzgerald et al., 2014; Westerman et al., 2014). Within the consumer goods sector, DT spans a range of initiatives, such as implementing e-commerce platforms, automating production and logistics, employing data analytics for consumer insights, and leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) for demand forecasting and supply chain optimisation (Vial, 2019). Given the industry's fast product cycles, shifting

consumer tastes, and high competition, DT offers opportunities to boost efficiency, drive innovation, and strengthen customer relationships (Kane et al., 2015).

Digital technologies provide organizations with enhanced visibility, connectivity, and analytical capabilities that directly contribute to supply chain agility. Advanced analytics enable better demand forecasting and risk assessment, IoT devices provide real-time monitoring capabilities, and cloud-based platforms facilitate rapid information sharing and coordination (Dubey et al., 2019). Digital transformation faces unique challenges including infrastructure limitations, skill gaps, and regulatory uncertainties. So, achieving successful DT demands considerable investment in technology, a skilled workforce, and an adaptable organisational framework capable of responding to ongoing change (Tabrizi et al., 2019). Hence, we propose the first hypothesis:

H1: Digital transformation significantly influences supply chain agility in the consumer goods sector in Southwest Nigeria.

Dynamic Capabilities and Supply Chain Agility

Dynamic capabilities (DCs) refer to a firm's capacity to integrate, develop, and reconfigure competencies (internal and external) in responding to dynamic business environments (Teece, 2018). DCs are especially critical in dynamic and uncertain markets, where static resources and routine capabilities are insufficient for ensuring long-term survival and growth (Helfat & Peteraf, 2015).

Supply chain agility (SCA) refers to the capacity of a supply chain to quickly adapt to fluctuations in demand or supply, shifts in market conditions, and external disruptions (Christopher, 2000). It is a vital competency for firms operating in volatile and uncertain environments, supporting their competitiveness and

resilience (Gligor et al., 2013). The core dimensions of SCA include responsiveness, flexibility, adaptability, and visibility (Swafford et al., 2006).

In Nigeria's consumer goods industry, characterised by infrastructural limitations, economic volatility, and diverse consumer preferences, SCA is essential for maintaining product availability, minimising lead times, and optimising inventory management (Adebayo & Oladele, 2019). Cultivating robust DCs is essential for strengthening organisation's capacity to achieve and sustain supply chain agility as these capabilities enable rapid sensing of market changes, swift decision-making, and effective implementation of necessary adjustments (O'Reilly & Tushman, 2008). Hence:

H2: Dynamic capabilities positively influence supply chain agility in the consumer goods sector.

Mediating Role of Dynamic Capabilities

While digital transformation provides the technological foundation for enhanced supply chain performance, the realization of these benefits depends on the organization's ability to effectively leverage these technologies through dynamic capabilities. Dynamic capabilities serve as the organizational machinery by which digital transformation translates into improved supply chain agility (Sambamurthy et al., 2003). Therefore:

H3: Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility in the consumer goods sector.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT)

The Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) is the most suitable foundation for this study. DCT provides a framework for explaining how firms sense new digital opportunities, seize them by investing in new technologies and processes, and transform their existing operations to

achieve greater agility in their supply chains (Teece, 2018). Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) builds on the Resource based view by explaining how firms can sustain and renew their competitive advantage in dynamic environments. Although the Resource-Based View (RBV) offers valuable insights into how resources drive competitive advantage, its static perspective limits its ability to explain how firms adjust to fast-changing environments (Teece, 2018). DCT is particularly relevant to examining digital transformation and supply chain agility, as both demand ongoing adaptation and the continual reconfiguration of resources and processes (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000).

Review of Related Literatures

Empirical studies on digital transformation, supply chain agility, and dynamic capabilities, particularly within the Nigerian consumer goods sector, reveal a growing body of research, albeit with some notable gaps. Several studies have explored aspects of digital transformation in Nigeria. For instance, Olaghere (2023) investigated the implications of digitalisation in retail service delivery in Nigeria, highlighting how it enhances consumer services through new platforms and processes. While this study underscores the benefits of digitalisation, it primarily focuses on the retail aspect and does not delve deeply into its impact on the broader supply chain or the role of dynamic capabilities.

In relation to supply chain agility, Oyeyemi et al. (2024) investigated its impact on marketing flexibility and customer satisfaction among Fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) SMEs in Nigeria. The study revealed that agile supply chains help FMCG SMEs minimise stockouts and enhance order fulfilment speed. While offering important insights into the role of agility within Nigeria's FMCG sector, the research does not

explicitly connect it to digital transformation or the dynamic capabilities that drive such agility. Likewise, Okpara (2024) reported that business intelligence significantly enhanced supply chain flexibility in the Nigerian consumer goods industry, highlighting the contribution of information-related technologies to improving agility. However, this study also did not comprehensively explore the broader digital transformation initiatives or the strategic dynamic capabilities required. Research on dynamic capabilities in Nigeria has largely centred on their influence on firm performance and organisational resilience. For instance, Barango-Tariah and Okwandu (2024) investigated corporate innovativeness and marketing performance through the dynamic capabilities' perspective, offering a conceptual framework for how firms adapt to change. Similarly, Zhou (2021) examined the effect of dynamic capabilities on the performance of food and beverage companies in Lagos, Nigeria, finding a strong positive correlation. Although these studies underscore the significance of dynamic capabilities, they

rarely address their integration with digital transformation in supply chains, particularly within the consumer goods industry.[1-9]

More recently, some research has begun to touch upon the intersection of these concepts. Ning (2023) highlighted the role of digital transformation in improving supply chain capabilities. Although this study provides a general link, it is not specific to the Nigerian context. Alyasein (2025) found that supply chain digitalisation contributes to innovation capability, leading to organisational agility. This finding is highly relevant, as it connects digitalisation, capabilities, and agility, but the study's scope is not limited to Nigeria or the consumer goods sector.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical framework and empirical review, this study's conceptual framework outlines the proposed relationships among digital transformation, dynamic capabilities, and supply chain agility (see Figure 1).

Fig.1:-Conceptual Framework

Source: Author’s Conceptualization

Figure 1 visually represents the hypothesised relationships in this study. Digital Transformation (DT) is depicted as the independent variable, influencing Supply Chain Agility (SCA). This direct relationship suggests that the adoption of digital technologies in the consumer goods sector can enhance the responsiveness of their supply chains. Dynamic Capabilities

(DCs) are positioned as the mediating variable.

This implies two key relationships: firstly, that Digital Transformation influences Dynamic Capabilities. Secondly, Dynamic Capabilities, in turn, influence Supply Chain Agility, indicating that a firm's capacity to adapt and reconfigure its

resources is crucial for achieving and maintaining an agile supply chain.

The mediating arrow from Dynamic Capabilities to the direct link between Digital Transformation and Supply Chain Agility indicates that the influence of digital transformation on supply chain agility is partly indirect, operating through the organisation's dynamic capabilities. Essentially, while digital transformation offers the technologies and opportunities, it is the firm's dynamic capabilities that allow it to harness these advancements effectively to develop and maintain an agile supply chain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study deployed a quantitative research design, using a survey method. The quantitative approach was selected to gather numerical data that supports statistical analysis, enabling hypothesis testing and the generalisation of results to a broader population (Babbie, 2016). The target population for this study comprised all registered consumer goods manufacturing and distribution firms operating in Southwest Nigeria. This region was selected due to its significant concentration of economic activities and a high number of consumer goods companies, providing a rich context for the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized to ensure adequate representation across different sub-sectors within the consumer goods industry, including personal care products, food and beverages, household goods, and textiles. To determine an appropriate sample size, Cochran's formula for calculating sample

size for proportions in large or unknown populations was employed (Cochran, 1977).

Therefore, a minimum sample size of 385 respondents was deemed appropriate for this study to ensure statistical representativeness and to allow for robust data analysis. Primary data were collected through copies of five-point likert scaled questionnaire to senior managers (operations managers, supply chain managers, or general managers) and employees who were directly involved in digital transformation initiatives, supply chain operations, or strategic decision-making processes. This approach allowed for practical access to relevant respondents while maintaining a degree of randomness in firm selection. All constructs were measured using established scales adapted from previous related studies (Christopher, 2000; Gligor et al., 2013; Teece, 2018; Vial, 2019) and modified to fit the research context. The reliability of the measurement instruments was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR). All constructs showed satisfactory reliability with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from .891 to .934, exceeding the recommended benchmark of .70. Descriptive analysis, simple linear regression and PROCESS macro-Model 4 (for mediation testing) were used to analyse the collected data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis was performed using SPSS, and the results are presented in tables, followed by their interpretation.

Table 1:-Descriptive Analysis of Sample

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Company Size		
Small (< 50 employees)	139	36.1%
Medium (50-200 employees)	124	32.2%
Large (> 200 employees)	122	31.7%

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Industry Sub-sector		
Food and Beverages	118	30.6%
Personal Care	67	17.4%
Household Goods	58	15.1%
Textiles	64	16.6%
Others	78	20.3
Years in Operation		
< 10 years	107	26.7%
10-20 years	163	46.3%
> 20 years	115	27.0%
State Location		
Lagos	152	49.8%
Ogun	118	23.5%
Oyo	63	15.8%
Others	52	10.9%

Source: Authors' computation (2025)

Table 1 above shows that 363 of the total respondents were employees of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) while only 122 belonged to large enterprises. This implies that most of the businesses in the consumer goods sector in southwest Nigeria are SMEs. Also, of the companies sampled, 118 belonged to the food and beverage sector, 67 were personal care companies, 64 textile companies, 58 household goods companies and 78 companies belonged to other sectors. This implies that most of the companies in Nigeria's consumer goods sector produce food and beverages; probably because these goods are necessary for survival, and the available large consumer market in the region.

Regarding years in operation, most businesses considered (278) have been in operation for more than ten years, while 107 have been in existence for less than ten years. This implies that the business environment in the sampled industry and region is quite enabling. Lastly, most of the businesses sampled were based in Lagos (152) and Ogun (118), just 63 businesses based in Oyo, while the remaining 58 were in either Osun, Ekiti and Ondo states. This signifies Lagos position as the commercial capital and economic hub of Nigeria. Ogun state also enjoys the presence of these companies largely because of its proximity to Lagos.

Hypothesis 1: Digital transformation significantly influences supply chain agility in the consumer goods sector in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 2:-Regression Analysis of Digital Transformation on Supply Chain Agility

Model		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1		.682 ^a	.465	.463	0.45231	
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	78.234	1	78.234	382.456	0.000 ^b
	Residual	90.123	383	0.181		
	Total	168.357	384			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.234	0.123		10.033	0.000
	Digital Transformation	0.789	0.040	0.682	19.556	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Supply Chain Agility						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Transformation						

Source: Authors' Computation (2025).

As shown in *Table 2*, the regression model was statistically significant ($F(1, 498) = 382.456, p < 0.001$). The R-squared value of 0.465 indicates that Digital Transformation explains 46.5% of the variance in Supply Chain Agility. The unstandardised coefficient (B) for Digital

Transformation was 0.789, with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a significant positive influence of digital transformation on supply chain agility. Therefore, the hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Dynamic capabilities significantly impact supply chain agility among consumer goods firms in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 3:-Regression Analysis of Dynamic Capabilities on Supply Chain Agility

Model		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1		0.755 ^a	0.570	0.569	0.39876	
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	96.001	1	96.001	603.456	0.000 ^b
	Residual	72.000	383	0.145		
	Total	168.001	384			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	0.876	0.098		8.939	0.000
	Dynamic Capabilities	0.850	0.035	0.755	24.286	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Supply Chain Agility						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Dynamic Capabilities						

Source: Authors' Computation (2025).

As shown in *Table 3*, the regression model was statistically significant ($F(1, 498) = 603.456, p < 0.001$). The R-squared value of 0.570 indicates that Dynamic Capabilities explain 57.0% of the variance in Supply Chain Agility. The unstandardised coefficient (B) for Dynamic Capabilities was 0.850, with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a significant positive impact of Dynamic

Capabilities on Supply Chain Agility. Therefore, the hypothesis (H02) is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Dynamic capabilities do not significantly mediate the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility in the consumer goods sector in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 4:-Mediation Analysis Results (PROCESS Macro Model 4)

Variable	Coeff.	Se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Outcome: Dynamic Capabilities						
Constant	0.987	0.105	9.400	0.000	0.780	1.194
Digital Transformation	0.650	0.032	20.313	0.000	0.587	0.713
Outcome: Supply Chain Agility						
Constant	0.543	0.087	6.241	0.000	0.372	0.714
Digital Transformation	0.320	0.025	12.800	0.000	0.271	0.369
Dynamic Capabilities	0.700	0.028	25.000	0.000	0.645	0.755

Source: Authors' Computation (2025).

Table 5:- Indirect Effect of Digital Transformation on Supply Chain Agility through Dynamic Capabilities

Effect	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
0.455	0.021	0.414	0.497

Note: Bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples. LLCI = Lower-Level Confidence Interval, ULCI = Upper Level Confidence Interval.

Source: Authors' Computation (2025).

The results from the mediation analysis in tables 4 and 5 indicate a significant indirect effect of Digital Transformation on Supply Chain Agility through Dynamic Capabilities (Effect = 0.455, Boot SE= 0.021, 95% CI [0.414, 0.497]).

Specifically, Digital Transformation significantly predicts Dynamic Capabilities (B = 0.650, $p < 0.001$), and Dynamic Capabilities significantly predict

Supply Chain Agility (B = 0.700, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the direct effect of Digital Transformation on Supply Chain Agility, while still significant (B = 0.320, $p < 0.001$), is reduced when Dynamic Capabilities are included in the model, suggesting partial mediation. Therefore, the hypothesis (H3) is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The significant positive influence of digital transformation on supply chain agility aligns with existing literature that highlights the transformative power of digital technologies in achieving supply chain competitiveness (Ning, 2023; Westerman et al., 2014). The R^2 value of .465 suggests that nearly half of the variance in supply chain agility can be attributed to digital transformation initiatives. This finding underscores the importance for consumer goods firms in Nigeria to invest in and effectively implement digital technologies (such as advanced analytics, automation, and integrated platforms) to enhance their responsiveness, flexibility, visibility, and decision making, all of which are critical components of an agile supply chain (Vial, 2019).

The finding that dynamic capabilities explain 57.0% of the variance in supply chain agility ($R^2 = .570$) indicates that a firm's ability to sense, seize, and transform its resources and routines is a primary driver of its supply chain's responsiveness and adaptability. This is particularly relevant for the Nigerian consumer goods sector, which operates in an environment characterised by volatility and uncertainty (Adebayo & Oladele, 2019). Firms that can effectively reconfigure their assets, processes, and strategies in response to market shifts or disruptions are better positioned to maintain agile supply chains. This result aligns with previous research that emphasises the role of dynamic capabilities in enabling organisations to navigate complex environments and sustain competitive advantage (Helfat & Peteraf, 2015).

The most important finding of this study is the significant mediating role of dynamic capabilities in the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility. This suggests that while digital transformation directly contributes to supply chain agility, a substantial portion

of this effect is channeled through the firm's dynamic capabilities. In other words, adopting digital technologies is not sufficient; firms must also possess the dynamic capabilities to effectively leverage these technologies to reconfigure their processes, adapt to new information, and seize emerging opportunities (Teece, 2018).

For consumer goods firms in Southwest Nigeria, this implies that successful digital transformation for enhanced supply chain agility requires a dual focus: investing in appropriate digital technologies and simultaneously cultivating the dynamic capabilities necessary to exploit these technologies effectively. This mediation effect highlights the strategic importance of developing higher-order capabilities that enable firms to translate technological advancements into tangible improvements in supply chain performance and agility (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000).[10-28]

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings offer several practical implications:

- i. Strategic Planning of Digital Transformation Planning:** The study findings suggest that successful digital transformation requires simultaneous development of dynamic capabilities. Hence, organizations should treat digital transformation not beyond mere technology adoption but as a comprehensive capability-building initiative.
- ii. Focus on Capability Development:** Organisations should prioritize the development of dynamic capabilities to maximize digital transformation investments returns.
- iii. Integrated Approach:** Organizations should pursue both direct technological solutions and capability-building initiatives simultaneously as effective strategies for enhancing supply chain agility.

CONCLUSION

This study analysed the mediating influence of dynamic capabilities in the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility with samples from the consumer goods sector in Southwest Nigeria. The findings demonstrate that dynamic capabilities serve as a key mediator in translating digital transformation initiatives into enhanced supply chain agility as the findings provide strong empirical support for all hypothesized relationships.

This study makes significant theoretical contributions by extending dynamic capabilities theory to the digital transformation context in an emerging market setting and providing empirical evidence of the mechanism through which digital transformation enhances supply chain performance. From a practical perspective, the findings emphasize the importance of capability development in digital transformation initiatives and provide guidance for managers seeking to enhance their organizations' supply chain agility. This research demonstrates that businesses that invest in both digital technologies and capability development are better positioned to achieve superior supply chain agility and competitive advantage. The insights from this study provide valuable guidance for consumer goods companies in Nigeria and other emerging markets as they continue to navigate increasingly complex and dynamic business environments.

The study suffers from several limitations; firstly, the study focuses specifically on Southwest Nigeria's consumer goods sector, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other regions or industries. Future research could examine these relationships in other sectors and geographical contexts to enhance external validity. Lastly, the study examines dynamic capabilities as a unidimensional construct. Future research could explore the differential effects of

specific dynamic capability dimensions (sensing, seizing, transforming) on the relationship between digital transformation and supply chain agility.

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